

Relativistic addition of velocities in a five-dimensional spacetime

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Abstract

Another method of adding relativistic velocities is shown. It uses a fifth dimension of spacetime rotating the coordinate system of the Minkowski diagram into it and thus is an indication of the existence of a fifth dimension. As proof of correctness of the rotation method it is derived from the addition theorem of velocities. Photographs of a hardware model illustrate how to find the resulting velocity by the rotation into the five-dimensional spacetime. Alongside the paradox “ $c + u' = c$ ” is resolved.

1. Introduction

In Minkowski diagrams relativistic addition of velocities according to the addition theorem of velocities can be illustrated [1]. For example $v = 0,6 c$ and $u' = 0,65 c$ results in $u = 0.899 c$

and in the according Minkowski diagram (fig.1) $u = \Delta x / \Delta t = (15.5 \text{ Ls}) / (17.2 \text{ s}) = 0.901 c$ can be read, which means the same numerical value within the accuracy of drawings.

Fig. 1: Minkowski diagram of a uniformly moved rocket in space at a speed of $v = 0.6 c$, which shoots protons at the coordinate origin in the direction of the movement at a speed of $u' = 0.65 c$. In the reference system S of the observer the protons move on the red worldline.

The oblique angled reference system S' with the coordinate axes x' and t' is the rest system of the rocket. One can imagine it being originated by turning the rectangular reference system S around the angle bisector by an angle φ into the fifth dimension (out of the drawing level), with the orthogonal projections of the axes x and t into the drawing level lying on the axes x' and t' .

Hereinafter is shown that after the turning the projection of the worldline of the body with the speed u' (a proton) in the rectangular coordinate system of the body with the speed v (the rocket) into the drawing level coincides with its (red) worldline in System S . This means that velocities can be added relativistic assuming the existence of a fifth dimension and using it that way.

2. The rotation angle

The angle φ depends on the velocity v or on v/c in this way:

$$\cos\varphi = \tan\left(\frac{\pi}{4} - \arctan\frac{v}{c}\right) \quad \text{for } 0 \leq v \leq c \quad (1)$$

Proof:

Fig. 2: Downside view (left) and side view (right) of the rotation of the angle δ out of the drawing level; ε is the orthogonal projection of the turned angle δ into the drawing level.

According to figure 2

$$b = a \cdot \cos\varphi$$

as well as

$$\tan\delta = a$$

and

$$\tan\varepsilon = b$$

So

$$\tan\varepsilon = a \cdot \cos\varphi$$

and

$$\mathbf{\tan\varepsilon = \tan\delta \cdot \cos\varphi.} \quad (2)$$

In the case of turning reference system S to reference system S' by the angle φ respectively the t -axis over the t' -axis

applies according to fig. 3 for the turned angle $\delta = 45^\circ$ and $\tan\delta = 1$. The angle $45^\circ - \alpha$ then takes the place of angle ε .

From (2) then follows

$$\tan\left(\frac{\pi}{4} - \alpha\right) = \cos\varphi$$

According to fig. 1 applies $\tan \alpha = \frac{v}{c}$
 and thus $\cos \varphi = \tan \left(\frac{\pi}{4} - \arctan \frac{v}{c} \right)$ s.a.

respectively $\varphi = \arccos \left(\tan(45^\circ - \alpha) \right)$ (3)
 for $0 \leq \alpha \leq 45^\circ$ (graphs see attachment fig. 12)

For $-45^\circ \leq \alpha \leq 0^\circ$ applies $\varphi = \arccos \left(\tan(45^\circ + \alpha) \right)$ Proof s. [2]
 The rotary axis in this case is the angle bisector in the 2. and 4. quadrant.

From the addition theorem of the tangent $\tan(x - y) = \frac{\tan x - \tan y}{1 + \tan x \cdot \tan y}$ follows from (1)

$$\cos \varphi = \frac{1 - \frac{v}{c}}{1 + \frac{v}{c}},$$

so $\cos \varphi = \frac{c-v}{c+v}$ for $0 \leq v \leq c$. (4)

$$\cos \varphi = \frac{c+v}{c-v} \quad \text{for } -c < v \leq 0 \quad \text{see [2]}$$

Now a second example is used to show that and how two relativistic velocities can be added by turning the rectangular coordinate system around the angle bisector w by the angle φ . For this the worldline of the second body (the proton, green in fig. 3) is drawn into the rectangular coordinate system. By the rotation by φ then the worldline of the second body in system S (red) results as the orthogonal projection of the turned (green) worldline of the second body.

In fig. 3 a rocket at the speed of $v = 0.2 c$ fires a proton with the speed $u' = 0.3 c$ in the rest system of the rocket. The t' -axis is the worldline of the rocket in system S , the green line is the worldline of the proton in S' before the turning and the red line is the worldline of the proton in S respectively the projection of its worldline in S' after the turning. So the resulting velocity can be found turning the green worldline by the angle φ .

Fig. 3: Minkowski-diagram for the relativistic addition of the velocities $v = 0.2 c$ and $u' = 0.3 c$; The addition theorem of velocities results in $u = 0.4717 c$, the drawing in $u=5.1 Ls / 10.8 s = 0.472 c$. (The rotation angle is $\varphi = 48.19^\circ$, measurable in fig. 10 in the attachment . With $\tan\gamma = \frac{u}{c} = 0.4717$ follows $\gamma = 25.25^\circ$, see below).

3. Proof of the procedure

As proof that the turning of S' into the fifth dimension exactly and in each case results in the same relativistic sum of velocities as the Minkowski diagram and as the addition theorem of velocities now is shown that the angle ε is the orthogonal projection of angle δ when δ was turned by the angle φ around the angle bisector w .

The from the Lorentz transformations derived addition theorem of velocities

$$u = \frac{u'+v}{1+\frac{u'v}{c^2}}$$

is assumed as true. In the

special cases with opposite orientations of the movements $v = c$ and $u' = -c$ as well as $v = -c$ and $u' = c$ however follows $u = 0/0$. Therefore this formula is valid only for all v with $|v| < c$ and all u' with $|u'| \leq c$. The restriction on $|v| < c$ makes sense physically, for a body emitting a quantum with velocity c or $-c$ cannot have lightspeed itself; and quanta at lightspeed do not emit quanta at lightspeed. In the theoretical special cases $v = c$ and $u' = c$ as well as $v = -c$ and $u' = -c$ however the addition theorem of velocities still applies.

As $c \neq 0$ applies $u = \frac{u'+v}{1+\frac{u'v}{c^2}} = \frac{(u'+v) \cdot c^2}{(1+\frac{u'v}{c^2}) \cdot c^2} = \frac{(u'+v) \cdot c^2}{c^2+u'v}$.

$$\Rightarrow u \cdot (c^2 + u'v) = (u' + v) \cdot c^2$$

as $(c^2 + u'v) \neq 0$ as per requirement $|v| < c$

$$\Rightarrow (u c^2 + u u'v) \cdot 2 = (u'c^2 + v c^2) \cdot 2$$

On both sides is added $+c^3 - uvc - uu'c + u'vc$.

$$\Rightarrow u c^2 + u u'v + u c^2 + u u'v = u'c^2 + v c^2 + u'c^2 + v c^2$$

$$\Rightarrow c^3 + u c^2 - v c^2 - u v c - u'c^2 - u u'c + u'v c + u u'v = c^3 + u'c^2 + v c^2 + u'v c - u c^2 - uvc - u u'c - u u'v$$

$$\Rightarrow c \cdot (c^2 + u c - v c - u v) - u' \cdot (c^2 + u c - v c - u v) = c \cdot (c^2 + v c + u'c + u'v) - u \cdot (c^2 + v c + u'c + u'v)$$

$$\Rightarrow (c - u') \cdot (c^2 + u c - v c - u v) = (c - u) \cdot (c^2 + v c + u'c + u'v)$$

$$\Rightarrow (c - u') [c(c + u) - v(c + u)] = (c - u) [c(c + v) + u'(c + v)]$$

$$\Rightarrow (c - u') (c - v) (c + u) = (c - u) (c + u') (c + v)$$

Now on both sides is divided by

$[(c + u') (c + v) (c + u)]$. For this must apply $u', v, u \neq -c$. $v \neq -c$ is required

above. Necessary at this point is the further restriction $u' \neq -c$. From $v \neq -c$ and $u' \neq -c$ follows $u \neq -c$ too.

$$\Rightarrow \frac{(c-u')}{(c+u')} \cdot \frac{(c-v)}{(c+v)} = \frac{(c-u)}{(c+u)} \quad (5)$$

From $1 \text{ Ls} = c \cdot 1 \text{ s}$ follows $v = \frac{s}{t} = \frac{a \text{ Ls}}{b \text{ s}} = \frac{a c s}{b s} = \frac{a}{b} c$ (s. fig. 1) $\Rightarrow \frac{v}{c} = \frac{a}{b}$

and from $\tan \alpha = \frac{a}{b}$ follows

$\tan \alpha = \frac{v}{c}$ and according fig. 3 $\tan \gamma = \frac{u}{c}$, $\tan (45^\circ - \delta) = \frac{u'}{c}$. (6)

For the first fraction in (5) applies with (6) $\frac{(c-u')}{(c+u')} = \frac{(c-u') \frac{1}{c}}{(c+u') \frac{1}{c}} = \frac{1-\frac{u'}{c}}{1+\frac{u'}{c}}$

$$= \frac{1-\tan(45^\circ-\delta)}{1+\tan(45^\circ+\delta)} = \frac{1-\frac{1-\tan \delta}{1+\tan \delta}}{1+\frac{1-\tan \delta}{1+\tan \delta}} = \frac{\frac{1+\tan \delta-(1-\tan \delta)}{1+\tan \delta}}{\frac{1+\tan \delta+1-\tan \delta}{1+\tan \delta}} = \frac{2 \tan \delta}{2} = \tan \delta .$$

For the second fraction in (5) applies $\frac{c-v}{c+v} = \cos \varphi$.

For the third fraction in (5) applies $\frac{(c-u)}{(c+u)} = \frac{(c-u)\frac{1}{c}}{(c+u)\frac{1}{c}} = \frac{1-\frac{u}{c}}{1+\frac{u}{c}}$

and with (6) $= \frac{1-\tan\gamma}{1+\tan\gamma} = \tan(45^\circ - \gamma)$.

From this follows for (5) $\tan\delta \cdot \cos\varphi = \tan(45^\circ - \gamma)$. (7)

According fig. 3 applies $45^\circ - \gamma = \varepsilon$. So the angles δ and ε of fig. 3 fulfil equation 2 $\tan\delta \cdot \cos\varphi = \tan\varepsilon$

for the rotation of an angle δ around one of its legs which here is the angle bisector by an angle φ and with the orthogonal projection ε of angle δ on the initial

surface. With this is shown that the relativistic addition of velocities can be done by the described procedure of the rotation of the rectangular reference system S' into a fifth dimension as well for all $|v| < c$ and all u' with $c < u' \leq c$.

4. Examples

This result shall be illustrated on the basis of the second example with $v = 0.2c$ and $u' = 0.3c$.

If a straight line is given by the unit vector $\begin{pmatrix} n_1 \\ n_2 \\ n_3 \end{pmatrix}$ then any point in \mathbb{R}^3 is turned by the rotation matrix

$$\begin{pmatrix} n_1^2(1 - \cos\alpha) + \cos\alpha & n_1n_2(1 - \cos\alpha) - n_3\sin\alpha & n_1n_3(1 - \cos\alpha) + n_2\sin\alpha \\ n_2n_1(1 - \cos\alpha) + n_3\sin\alpha & n_2^2(1 - \cos\alpha) + \cos\alpha & n_2n_3(1 - \cos\alpha) - n_1\sin\alpha \\ n_3n_1(1 - \cos\alpha) - n_2\sin\alpha & n_3n_2(1 - \cos\alpha) + n_1\sin\alpha & n_3^2(1 - \cos\alpha) + \cos\alpha \end{pmatrix}$$

by the angle α around that straight line [3]. For $\alpha := \varphi = 48.19^\circ$ and the unit vector of the angle bisector between the coordinate axes x and t $\begin{pmatrix} 1/\sqrt{2} \\ 1/\sqrt{2} \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}$ follows

the rotation matrix

$$\begin{pmatrix} 0.8333 & 0.1666 & 0.5270 \\ 0.1667 & 0.8333 & -0.5270 \\ -0.5270 & 0.5270 & 0.6667 \end{pmatrix} .$$

The point (3|10|0) of the worldline of the proton in framework S' before the turning is mapped by this matrix to the point (4.167|8.833|3.629) which is positioned exactly over the worldline of the proton in framework S . For with $\tan\gamma = 4.167/8.833$ follows $\gamma = 25.26^\circ$,

which is the same angle as calculated at fig. 3 (the difference of 0.01° is a rounding error), i.e. the turned green worldline actually is positioned above the red worldline.

This means, that instead of the addition theorem of velocities or a Minkowski diagram a rotation matrix can be used, for with $\tan\gamma = u/c$ follows $u = 0.4718c$ (the difference of 0.0001 is a rounding error).

Moreover the angle γ and from that the velocity u can be calculated with analytical geometry using the rotating by the angle φ too [5] (see the lines d and e in fig. 5).

The 5d-model is confirmed at a hardware-model, see the photographs in figures 5, 6, 8, 9. Cameras do not produce parallel projections but central projections. That is why there are slight

distortions and the right point of taking the pictures had to be chosen from a distance as large as possible. So the pictures had to be enlarged which caused fuzziness.

Fig. 5: Right-angled geo-triangle rotated by the angle φ at $v = 0.2 c$ and $u' = 0.3 c$. The dark worldline of the proton on the geo-triangle transitions differentially into its red worldline in coordinate system S (the gap is caused by the flattened edge of the geo-triangle).

Fig. 6: The same object as in fig. 5 in side views which are orthogonal to each other; because of the central projection the angle φ is a bit bigger than 48.19° (50.5°). The parallel projection in fig. 10 shows an angle $\varphi = 48.2^\circ$.

Parallel projections on the other hand are produced by a computer code written with GNU Octave [4] (see attachment and fig. 7).

Fig. 7: The example of fig. 3 and 5, left side the spatial representation with the axes x , t and x_5 , the blue worldline for $v = 0.2 c$, the dotted green worldline for $u' = 0.3 c$, the red worldline of the resulting velocity $u = 0.4717 c$, the turned black t -axis and the turned green worldline. Right side the vertical projection shows that the blue worldline is the exact projection of the t -axis and the red worldline is the exact projection of the turned green worldline because at the upper ends the covered lines (red and blue) are partially visible.

By clicking at GNU Octave the icon with the double arrow (rotate) in one of the figures 7 the figure can be rotated respectively the point of view can be changed. This way the vertical projection

can be produced. The computer program "Video_turning_to_plan.mp4" (see attachment after fig. 9) shows this rotation from an oblique view to the plan.

Fig. 8: Comparison of the central projection (left side) and the parallel projection (right side) for $v = 0.3 c$ and $u' = 0.8 c$ ($u = 0.8871 c$). The red worldline is covered by the green worldline. Comparable angles are equal in the left and right picture; they are independent of the scales. See also attachment fig. 9.

The resulting velocity u can also be calculated by means of analytic geometry using the blue lines g , d and e in fig. 3. And

u can as well be calculated from the angles φ , α and β' (see fig. 9).

5. Resolution of the paradox " $c + u' = c$ "

In this five-dimensional model of the world resolves the paradox " $c + u' = c$ " which was confirmed by an experiment at CERN in 1964, when pi-mesons with $v = 0.99975 c$ emitted gamma-rays in the direction of movement, the velocity of which was measured as c . In the

theoretical or approximate case of $v = c$ the worldline of the first object is the angle bisector and the turning angle results in $\varphi = 90^\circ$. Then the orthogonal projection of the worldline of the second object of any velocity in S' coincides with the angle bisector in S , see fig. 9.

Fig. 9: Left side applies $0 \leq \varphi < 90^\circ$, right side applies $\varphi = 90^\circ$. If $\varphi = 90^\circ$ the orthogonal projection of the green worldline of the second object coincides with the angle bisector w for any angle β' ($0 < \beta' \leq 45^\circ$). So the resulting velocity in S always is c . Paradoxically the first and the second object move together in S although the first object emits the second one. But in the fifth dimension they move away from each other at the speed u' .

6. Summary

The shown method of adding relativistic velocities together with the derivation of the addition theorem of velocities supports the ingenious idea of Theodor Kaluza, who introduced a fifth dimension as the first one in 1921 [6], as well as the

Kaluza-Klein-theory [7]. Furthermore a five-dimensional spacetime may give the possibility to explain quantum entanglement and the orbitals of atoms being standing waves of the three-dimensional space.

6. Acknowledgement

Thanks to the author at the science forum matheplanet.de with the pseudonym MontyPythagoras, who doubted in the existence of a fifth dimension which I found in a preceding manuscript for matheplanet.de in 2022. He particularly gave the example of the relativistic addition of velocities as contradiction to

a fifth dimension. That challenged me to deal with this subject and show that it is working within a five-dimensional spacetime. Thereby I found an even stronger indication for the existence of a fifth dimension than in the previous manuscript.

Further thanks to Jonas Kaiser who gave me the idea to produce perfect

projections of worldlines with GNU Octave by doing that with freeCAD.

References

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Attachment

GNU-Octave-Program for fig. 7:

```

1 # Relativistic_addition_of_velocities_in_RS
2 # Minkowski-diagram with rotation by the angle bisector
3
4 # t = (c/v)*x = (1/a) * x ; c/u' = 1/b
5 a=0.2 ; disp('v/c = '); a
6 b=0.3 ; disp('u'/c = '); b
7 x=linspace(0,5,50);
8 t1=(1/a)*x; t2=(1/b)*x; # worldlines of a 1st and a 2nd body in S
9 z=linspace(0,5,50);
10 clf; figure(1);
11 plot3(x,t1,0*z,'b'); # worldline of a 1st body in S
12 axis equal; grid on; hold on;
13 plot3(x,t2,0*z,'--g'); # worldline of the 2nd body (dotted green) before rotation
14 plot3(x,x,0*z,'--k'); # angle bisector (dotted black) in S
15 p=0:pi/2; # p = phi # rotation angle
16 disp('rotation angle phi := p')
17 p=acos(tan((pi/4)-atan(a)))
18 phi=(p/pi)*180
19 q=sqrt(2);
20 A=[0;5;0]; plot3(A(1),A(2),A(3),'*k')
21 B=[2;2/b;0]; plot3(B(1),B(2),B(3),'*g')
22 R=[(1-cos(p))/2+cos(p), (1-cos(p))/2, sin(p)/q; (1-cos(p))/2, (1-cos(p))/2+cos(p), -sin(p)/q; -sin(p)/q, -sin(p)/q, sin(p)/q, cos(p)];
23 # R = rotation matrix for rotation around the angle bisector
24 disp('rotation matrix R'); R
25 E=R*A; plot3(E(1),E(2),E(3),'*k')
26 F=R*B; plot3(F(1),F(2),F(3),'*g')
27 disp('location vector of point F'); F
28 plot3(E(1)*x,E(2)*x,E(3)*x,'k'); # t'-axis = turned worldline of the 1st body in S' (black)
29 plot3(F(1)*x,F(2)*x,F(3)*x,'g'); # turned worldline of the 2nd body in S' (green)
30 # worldline of the 2nd body in S:
31 plot3(F(1)*x,F(2)*x,0*x,'r'); # projection of the green worldline from S' to S (red)
32 xlim([-0.01 5+0.01])
33 ylim([0 10])
34 zlim([0 4])
35 xlabel('x/Ls'); ylabel('t/s'); zlabel('x5/Ls')
36 title('Relativistic addition of velocities in RS')
37 disp('u/c =')
38 d=F(1)/F(2) # wanted resulting velocity u/c of the 2nd body in S

39
40 # for comparison calculation with the addition theorem
41 # uc=(u'+v)/(1+u'*v/c^2) = [(a + b)/(1 + a*b)] c
42 hold off; disp(' ')
43 disp('comparison with the addition theorem:')
44 d=(a+b)/(1+a*b)
45
46 # the same diagram in vertical projection:
47 figure(2); clf; hold on; grid on; axis equal;
48 plot3(x,t1,0*z,'b'); # worldline of the 1st body (blue) in S
49 plot3(x,t2,0*z,'--g'); # worldline of the 2nd body (dotted green) before rotation
50 plot3(x,x,0*z,'--k'); # angle bisector (dotted black) in S
51 A=[0;5;0]; plot3(A(1),A(2),A(3),'*k')
52 B=[2;2/b;0]; plot3(B(1),B(2),B(3),'*g')
53 E=R*A; plot3(E(1),E(2),E(3),'*k')
54 F=R*B; plot3(F(1),F(2),F(3),'*g')
55 plot3(E(1)*x,E(2)*x,E(3)*x,'k'); # t'-axis = turned worldline of the 1st body in S' (black)
56 plot3(F(1)*x,F(2)*x,F(3)*x,'g'); # turned worldline of the 2nd body in S' (green)
57 plot3(F(1)*x,F(2)*x,0*x,'r'); # projection of the green worldline from S' to S (red)
58 xlim([-0.01 5])
59 ylim([0 10])
60 zlim([0 4])
61 xlabel('x/Ls'); ylabel('t/s'); zlabel('x5/Ls')
62 title('Fig. 1 in vertical projection')
63 hold off;

```

First type this code into the editor window (as shown here), because it can be corrected only there. Store it with a name followed by .m ; then copy it to the command window and start it with that name, but without .m

Fig. 9: : Comparison of the central projection (left side) and the parallel projection (right side) for $v = 0.6 c$ and $u' = 0.6 c$ ($u = 0.8824 c$).

GNU-Octave-program for the "Video_turning_to_plan.mp4":

```

1  fn='Video_turning_to_plan.mp4';
2  w=VideoWriter(fn);
3  a=0.7;    b=0.3;
4  x=linspace(0,5,50);
5  z=linspace(0,5,50);
6  p=0:pi/2;
7  p=acos(tan((pi/4)-atan(a)));
8  q=sqrt(2);
9  R=[(1-cos(p))/2+cos(p), (1-cos(p))/2, sin(p)/q; (1-cos(p))/2, (1-cos(p))/2+cos(p), -sin(p)/q; -sin(p)/q, sin(p)/q, cos(p)];
10
11 figure(301); clf; grid on; axis equal;
12 xlim([-0.01 5+0.01])
13 ylim([0 8])
14 zlim([0 4])
15 hold on; view(3)
16 h=plot3(5.01,8,4,'.');
17 title('Turning to plan')
18 xlabel('x/Ls'); ylabel('t/s'); zlabel('x5')
19
20 for n=1:301
21     t1=(1/a)*x;
22     t2=(1/b)*x;
23     plot3(x,t1,0*z,'b');
24     view([-5+(5/300)*(n-1), -20+(20/300)*(n-1), 4+(30/300)*(n-1)]);
25     plot3(x,t2,0*z,'--g');
26     plot3(x,x,0*z,'--k');
27     A=[0;5;0];    plot3(A(1),A(2),A(3),'*k')
28     B=[2;2/b;0];  plot3(B(1),B(2),B(3),'*g')
29     E=R*A;        plot3(E(1),E(2),E(3),'*k')
30     F=R*B;        plot3(F(1),F(2),F(3),'*g')
31     plot3(E(1)*x,E(2)*x,E(3)*x,'k');
32     plot3(F(1)*x,F(2)*x,F(3)*x,'g');
33     plot3(F(1)*x,F(2)*x,0*x,'r');
34     drawnow;
35     writeVideo(w,getframe(gcf));
36 endfor
37 close(w)

```

Recommendation: First type in the command window 'pkg load video', copy the code to the command window and start it with 'open Video_turnig_to_plan.mp4'.

```
>> Relativistic_addition_of_velocitie
v/c =
a = 0.2000
u'/c =
b = 0.3000
rotation angle phi := p
p = 0.8411
phi = 48.190
rotation matrix R
R =
    0.8333    0.1667    0.5270
    0.1667    0.8333   -0.5270
   -0.5270    0.5270    0.6667

location vector of point F
(green point rotated at phi)
F =
    2.7778
    5.8889
    2.4595

u/c = F(1)/F(2) =
d = 0.4717

comparison with the addition theorem:
d = 0.4717
>> |
```


Fig. 10: Parallel projection of example 2 with $v = 0.2 c$, $u' = 0.3 c$ and $\varphi = 48,19^\circ$. The measurement of φ in the turned left diagram gives the angle 48.2° .